

Supplementary Figure 1. Potential bacterial contaminants. Mean relative abundance in aerosols and topsoils desert samples of zOTUs identified as potential bacterial contaminants. zOTUs were grouped by genus.

Supplementary Figure 2. Potential eukaryal contaminants. Mean relative abundance in aerosols and topsoils desert samples of zOTUs identified as potential eukaryal contaminants. The zOTUs were grouped according to the most specific taxonomic level available.

Supplementary Figure 3. Temporal autocorrelation of airborne communities for each air masses origin. Mantel correlogram with spearman method for temporal autocorrelation of airborne communities based on Bray-Curtis distances, for bacteria and eukaryotes (mostly fungi). Distance class index is shown for years. Bold points indicate significant temporal autocorrelation with Holm correction of the p-values for multiple testing (p-value < 0.05, 1,000 permutations), mainly in the temporally closest communities of Atlantic, European and local origin.

Supplementary Figure 4. Ordination of African airborne communities according to geographical distribution. Non-metric multidimensional scale (NMDS) ordination of African airborne communities based on Bray-Curtis distances, for bacteria and eukaryotes (mostly fungi). The African origins of aerosols (east and west) estimated by backward trajectories are shown.

Supplementary Figure 5. Frequency and desert origin of air ubiquitous immigrants for each origin. Mean relative abundance and occupancy relationship of the air ubiquitous zOTUs for each origin, for bacteria and eukaryotes (mostly fungi). zOTUs that co-occur in the desert of Libya, Morocco and Senegal are shown in red, green and blue, respectively. zOTUs that not do co-occur in deserts are shown in purple. The x-axis and y-axis dotted lines divide zOTUs detected in >50% of samples and >1% relative abundance for each origin, respectively.

Supplementary Figure 6. Relative abundances of microorganisms in desert soil versus air. Mean relative abundance of zOTUs in desert soil, and in the air for each origin, for bacteria and eukaryotes (mostly fungi). Desert zOTUs that co-occur with ubiquitous and non-ubiquitous airborne zOTUs are shown in black and red, respectively. Desert zOTUs not detected in the air are shown in the left panels in brown; n means the number of zOTUs. The x-axis and y-axis dotted lines divide zOTUs detected in >1% relative abundance.

Supplementary Figure 7. Relative abundance of air bacteria in topsoils from north African deserts and world's biomes. Mean relative abundance in soils of airborne zOTUs were differentiated according to their detection in air.

Supplementary Figure 8. High altitude air mass tracking of rain events. Back-trajectories (14-days) at 3000 (A), 6000 (B) and 8000 (C) m asl of rainfall events at the collection site for the period 1987-2014, separated according to African, Atlantic, European and local origins. Sampling sites for rains (blue dot) and desert samples (yellow dots) are indicated on the maps. Map data: Google, TerraMetrics.

Supplementary Figure 9. Air mass tracking of Atlantic rains. Back-trajectories (96-h) at 6000 m asl of 3, 6, 9, 12 and 15 days before the rainfall events at the sampling site for the period 1987-2014, for aerosols associated with adjacent Atlantic currents. Map data: Google, TerraMetrics.

Supplementary Figure 10. Air mass tracking of European rains. Back-trajectories (96-h) at 6000 m asl of 3, 6, 9, 12 and 15 days before the rainfall events at the sampling site for the period 1987-2014, for aerosols associated with adjacent European currents. Map data: Google, TerraMetrics.

Supplementary Figure 11. Air mass tracking of local rains. Back-trajectories (96-h) at 6000 m asl of 3, 6, 9, 12 and 15 days before the rainfall events at the sampling site for the period 1987-2014, for aerosols associated with adjacent local currents. Map data: Google, TerraMetrics.

Supplementary Table 1. Metadata for aerosol and desert soil samples.

Supplementary Table 2. PERMANOVA pairwise comparisons of airborne and desert bacterial and eukaryal communities. R² values are shown.

Supplementary Table 3. 167 zOTUs of the air core for bacterial communities with mean abundance and occupancy in aerosol samples by origin, mean abundance in deserts, and taxonomy.

Supplementary Table 4. Sequences of 167 zOTUs of the air core for bacterial communities.

Supplementary Table 5. 92 OTUs of the air core for eukaryal communities, with mean abundance and occupancy in aerosol samples by origin, mean abundance in deserts, and taxonomy.

Supplementary Table 6. Sequences of 92 zOTUs of the air core for eukaryal communities.